

Microbiological profile and antimicrobial resistance in ventriculoperitoneal shunt infections at a tertiary hospital in Central India

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Hydrocephalus is characterized by the abnormal accumulation of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) within the brain, resulting in elevated intracranial pressure. A ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunt diverts excess CSF to the peritoneal cavity to relieve this pressure. However, VP shunt placement carries a significant risk of device-related infection, most of which occur within the first three months after surgery. The recent emergence of multidrug-resistant pathogens has heightened concerns, likely reflecting widespread and sometimes inappropriate antibiotic use.

OBJECTIVE: To characterize the microbiological profile and antimicrobial resistance patterns of VP shunt infections, with the goal of informing the hospital's antibiotic stewardship policy.

METHODS: A single-center prospective observational cohort study was conducted from February to July 2024. Cerebrospinal fluid samples were aseptically collected from VP shunt chambers and by shunt tapping and cultured using standard microbiological techniques. Antimicrobial susceptibility was assessed using Kirby–Bauer disc diffusion method and interpreted according to the 2024 CLSI guidelines. Statistical significance was evaluated using the Chi-square and Fisher's exact tests.

RESULTS: VP shunt infection occurred in 44.4% of the cases. The most frequently isolated organisms were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (16.7%), *Acinetobacter* species (9.3%), and *Escherichia coli* (7.4%); *Burkholderia cepacia* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were each detected in 1.9% of the cases. Gram-negative isolates exhibited higher antimicrobial resistance than Gram-positive organisms. Re-shunting was required in 31.5% of patients, and the overall mortality rate was 14.8%.

CONCLUSIONS: This study revealed an alarmingly high (44.4%) infection rate accompanied by substantial antimicrobial resistance. Rigorous aseptic techniques, early diagnosis, prompt targeted therapy, and strict adherence to antimicrobial stewardship protocols are essential to reduce morbidity and mortality associated with VP shunt infections.

Keywords: Hydrocephalus, ventriculoperitoneal shunt, infection, brain tumor, Central India

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INTRODUCTION

Hydrocephalus is characterized by the abnormal accumulation of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) within the brain, leading to increased intracranial pressure. It can result from various conditions, including intracranial tumors, congenital brain malformations, and disturbances in CSF production or drainage. Ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunt placement is one of the most common neurosurgical procedures for managing hydrocephalus, diverting excess CSF to the peritoneal cavity, and thereby reducing intracranial pressure [1].

Infection remains one of the most serious complications of VP shunting, occurring in approximately 10–15% of cases [2]. VP shunt infection is typically diagnosed when a positive CSF bacterial culture is accompanied by CSF pleocytosis, fever, neurological symptoms, and evidence of shunt malfunction [3, 4]. Diagnosis may also be supported by a positive blood culture in patients presenting with altered sensorium, headache, peritonitis, vomiting, or new-onset seizures. These infections can cause seizures, cognitive decline, and a twofold increase in long-term mortality [5,6].

Recognized risk factors include young age, prematurity, previous shunt infection, prolonged operative time, multiple shunt systems, postoperative CSF leakage, repeated handling of shunt hardware, catheter contamination, poor skin condition, and high personnel traffic in the operating theatre [7–9]. More than 60% of infections arise within four to five weeks following shunt placement. Early infections are usually linked to breaches in the sterile technique during insertion, whereas late infections often result from the secondary spread of abdominal pathology, such as peritonitis or bowel perforation [10]. VP shunt infections frequently progress to ventriculitis or meningitis [11].

Historically, Gram-positive organisms, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, coagulase-negative staphylococci, and *Enterococcus* species, have been the predominant pathogens causing VP shunt infections. However, in the past decade, Gram-negative bacilli such as *Acinetobacter* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., and members of the *Enterobacteriales* family, have become increasingly important [11]. The 2023 ICMR annual report on the Antimicrobial Resistance Research and Surveillance Network noted that Gram-negative bacteria predominated among CSF isolates, suggesting a high rate of hospital-acquired ventriculitis in the study group. The predominant Gram-negative pathogen identified was *Acinetobacter baumannii* (28.18%), with *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (17.75%) as the next most common, followed by *Escherichia coli* (11.34%), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

(7.56%), while Gram-positive *S. aureus* accounted for 4.12% [12].

Treatment typically begins with intravenous and intraventricular antibiotic therapies. Definitive treatment often requires complete removal of the infected shunt, placement of an external ventricular drain to control intracranial pressure, and later insertion of a new contralateral shunt once the infection has cleared [13–15].

The global rise in multidrug-resistant (MDR) organisms, which is believed to be due to inappropriate antibiotic use in both community and hospital settings, has intensified the challenge of treating VP shunt infections [11].

The ICMR 2023 report highlighted the particularly poor susceptibility of *A. baumannii* isolated from CSF samples to second- and fourth-generation cephalosporins, β -lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitor combinations, fluoroquinolones, and carbapenems, whereas *P. aeruginosa* remained relatively more susceptible to these antimicrobial agents [12]. Therefore, mortality in neurosurgical infections caused by carbapenem-resistant Gram-negative bacteria can reach 60–70% [11].

Despite these concerns, data on the microbiological profiles of VP shunt infections in many regions remain limited. This single-center prospective study aimed to characterize the causative organisms of VP shunt infections and their antimicrobial resistance patterns, provide evidence to guide antibiotic policies, and improve outcomes in affected patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and setting

This single-center prospective observational cohort study evaluating the microbiological profile and antimicrobial resistance of VP shunt-associated infections was conducted in the Department of Microbiology at a tertiary care hospital in Central India between February and July 2024. CSF samples from all VP shunt procedures performed during this six-month period were included.

The Institutional Ethics Committee approved this study (approval no. 308, February 2024), and written informed consent was obtained from all the participants or their legal guardians.

Sample collection

A total of 54 CSF samples were collected under strict aseptic precautions either from the VP shunt chamber

or by shunt tapping (Fig. 1). Each specimen represented a distinct patient, and no repeat samples were analyzed, except for two repeat samples with coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS) from two patients.

Perioperative infection-control measures

Prior to surgery, the operating surgeon performed a five-minute antiseptic hand scrub. All instruments were sterilized by autoclaving, patients underwent standard pre-anesthetic evaluation, and prophylactic antibiotics were administered. The operating theatre was maintained using a high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filter to ensure sterility.

Bacteriological Culture and Identification

CSF samples were cultured on blood agar, MacConkey agar, and chocolate agar (HiMedia, Maharashtra, India). The plates were incubated at 37°C for 48–72 h. *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 and *E. coli* ATCC 25922 were used as reference strains for Gram-positive and Gram-negative controls, respectively. After incubation, the isolates were identified by Gram staining, colony morphology, and standard biochemical tests, in accordance with established microbiological protocols [16]. Advanced

automated methods, such as MALDI-TOF or VITEK, have not been employed for confirmatory identification.

Diagnostic Criteria

VP shunt infection was diagnosed when all the following were present:

1. Positive culture from CSF sample obtained from the shunt reservoir or catheter tip,
2. Compatible clinical findings (fever, neurological symptoms, headache, tenderness, nausea or vomiting) or evidence of shunt malfunction, and
3. Supportive CSF parameters, including pleocytosis or leukocytosis.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing

Antimicrobial susceptibility was determined using the Kirby–Bauer disc diffusion method on Mueller–Hinton agar with commercially available discs (HiMedia, Maharashtra, India). The following antibiotics were tested: ceftazidime (30 µg), ceftazidime/avopivoxin (30/30 µg), cefepime (30 µg), amoxicillin/clavulanate (20/10 µg), piperacillin/tazobactam (100/10 µg), meropenem (10 µg), aztreonam (30 µg), and levofloxacin (5 µg).

Fig. 1. Flowchart of sample selection and clinical outcomes.

Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of vancomycin for *S. aureus* and coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS) and of meropenem and levofloxacin for *Burkholderia cepacia* were determined using the E-test. Screening for extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) and carbapenemase production was performed, and the results were interpreted according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines, 2024 edition [17].

Statistical analysis

The data were analyzed at a 95% confidence level. Associations between categorical variables were assessed using the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, as appropriate, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Of the 54 CSF samples analyzed, 24 (44.4%) showed bacterial growth. Samples were obtained from 29 males (53.7%) and 25 females (46.3%); however, positive cultures were evenly distributed between the sexes (12 males and 12 females).

Most infections occurred in children aged 0–10 years (14.8%), followed by patients aged >40 years (12.9%)

and those aged 31–40 years (11.1%). Fewer cases were observed in the 11–20-year age group (5.5%), and no infections were detected in the 21–30-year age group. Among the youngest infected patients, six (11.1%) were under five years of age (Table 1).

A χ^2 test of independence was performed to compare the infection rates across age groups. The analysis yielded $\chi^2 = 5.55$ with four degrees of freedom, giving a p -value of 0.236, indicating no statistically significant association between age group and VP shunt infection. Fisher's exact test was used to assess the relationship between age group and mortality. This analysis produced a p -value of 0.085, showing no significant association between age and mortality among patients with VP shunts.

The major risk factors for VP shunt infection in this study were brain tumors (54.1%), congenital hydrocephalus (33.3%), and low birth weight (16.7%). Developmental delay and central nervous system (CNS) infection each accounted for 4.2% of the cases, whereas head trauma was not identified as a risk factor (Table 2). Notably, all four patients with low birth weight also had congenital hydrocephalus, indicating a strong correlation between these two conditions.

To assess the association between each individual risk factor and infection status, Fisher's exact test was used. Congenital hydrocephalus was the only

Table 1. Age distribution, infection status, and mortality among VP shunt patients (n=54)

Age group (years)	Infected patients n (%)	Non-infected patients n (%)	Total patients n (%) ^a	Mortality ^b n (%)
0–10	8 (14.8)	6 (11.1)	14 (25.9)	1 (1.9)
11–20	3 (5.5)	4 (7.4)	7 (13.0)	3 (5.5)
21–30	0 (0)	4 (7.4)	4 (7.4)	1 (1.9)
31–40	6 (11.1)	4 (7.4)	10 (18.5)	0 (0)
>40	7 (12.9)	12 (22.2)	19 (35.2)	3 (5.5)
Total	24 (44.4)	30 (55.6)	54 (100)	8 (14.8)

^a Percentages for "Total patients" reflect the proportion of the overall cohort (n = 54).

^b Mortality indicates deaths within each age group, regardless of infection status.

Table 2. Underlying risk factors for VP shunt infection (n=54)

Risk factor	Infected patients n (%) ^a	Non-infected patients n (%)	p value ^b (χ^2 test)
Congenital hydrocephalus	8 (33.3)	2 (6.6)	0.016*
Low birth weight	4 (16.7)	2 (6.6)	0.15
Brain tumor	13 (54.1)	19 (63.3)	0.67
Developmental delay	1 (4.2)	3 (10.0)	1.00
CNS infection	1 (4.2)	1 (3.3)	1.00
Head trauma	0 (0)	2 (6.6)	0.497
Total	24 (100)	30 (100)	—

^a Percentages are based on the number of infected patients (n=24) and non-infected patients (n=30).

* $p < 0.05$ (bolded) indicates a statistically significant association.

factor significantly associated with VP shunt infection ($p=0.016$), indicating that patients with this condition were more likely to develop infection following shunt placement. All other risk factors showed no statistically significant association with VP shunt infection ($p>0.05$).

The most frequent clinical symptoms among patients with infected VP shunts were headache and vomiting (each 41.7%), followed by diminished vision and fever (each 20.8%). Dizziness occurred in 12.5% of cases, whereas limb weakness, seizures, and altered sensorium were each observed in 8.3% of the patients (Table 3).

Table 3. Clinical symptoms in patients with infected VP shunts (n=24)

Symptom	Patients n (%)
Headache	10 (41.7)
Vomiting	10 (41.7)
Diminished vision	5 (20.8)
Fever	5 (20.8)
Dizziness	3 (12.5)
Limb weakness	2 (8.3)
Seizure	2 (8.3)
Altered sensorium	2 (8.3)
Other symptoms ^a	6 (25.0)

^a Other symptoms included irritability (n=2), gait disturbance (n=1), and decreased hearing (n=3).

A total of 24 patients had infected VP shunts, and several presented with two or more clinical symptoms. Biochemical analysis revealed elevated white blood cell (WBC) counts in 29.2% of infected patients, deranged liver function in 4.2% of patients, and renal impairment in 16.7% of patients. Of all CSF samples, 22 of 54 (40.7%) demonstrated monomicrobial growth, whereas 2 of 54 (3.7%) showed polymicrobial growth. The most frequent isolate was *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (16.7%), followed by *Acinetobacter* species (9.3%), and *E. coli* (7.4%). *Burkholderia cepacia*, *S. aureus*, and *Candida* species were each detected in 1.9% of cases (Table 4).

Table 4. Microbiological profile and associated mortality rates of patients with infected VP shunt (n=54)

Microorganism	Patients n (%)	Mortality n (%)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	9 (16.7)	1 (1.9)
<i>Acinetobacter</i> spp.	5 (9.3)	2 (3.7)
<i>E. coli</i>	4 (7.4)	2 (3.7)
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	3 (5.4)	0 (0)
CoNS	2 (3.6)	0 (0)
<i>S. aureus</i>	1 (1.9)	0 (0)
<i>Burkholderia cepacia</i>	1 (1.9)	0 (0)
<i>Candida</i> spp.	1 (1.9)	0 (0)
No microbial growth	30 (55.5)	2 (3.7)

Fisher's exact test was performed to assess the statistical significance of the association between the type of infecting organism and mortality rate, yielding a p-value of 0.015. This result indicates a statistically significant relationship between the infecting microorganisms and patient mortality. Notably, high mortality was observed among patients infected with *Acinetobacter* spp. and *E. coli*, whereas no deaths occurred in patients infected with other organisms ($p=0.048$).

The antimicrobial resistance patterns of Gram-positive cocci isolated from various samples are shown in Fig. 2. In our study, these isolates exhibited the highest resistance to penicillin (100%) and ceftazidime (*S. aureus*), followed by gentamicin (33.3%, data not shown), which was observed in one *S. aureus* isolate. Importantly, systemic administration of gentamicin does not achieve sufficient CSF concentrations due to limited blood-brain barrier penetration. Therefore, direct administration of gentamicin into the shunt reservoir or via the intraventricular route may be required for efficient treatment of VP shunt infections. No resistance was detected against vancomycin or linezolid. It should be noted that CoNS were isolated from repeat samples in two patients and were therefore included in the total sample count.

The antimicrobial resistance profiles of Enterobacteriales, including *E. coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, are presented in Fig. 3. *E. coli* exhibited the highest resistance to aztreonam (75%), followed by cefotaxime and cefepime (50% each). In contrast, *K. pneumoniae* showed the highest resistance to cefotaxime (77.8%), followed by levofloxacin (66.6%). Minimal resistance was observed against piperacillin-tazobactam, meropenem and levofloxacin in *E. coli* (25%) and to gentamicin in both species (*E. coli*, 25%; *K. pneumoniae*, 11.1%, data not shown). None of the isolates tested positive for extended-spectrum beta-lactamase or carbapenemase production.

The antimicrobial resistance profiles of non-fermenting organisms, including *Pseudomonas* spp., *Acinetobacter* spp., and *Burkholderia cepacia*, are presented in Fig. 4. Overall, higher resistance rates were observed for *Acinetobacter* spp. and *B. cepacia* than for *Pseudomonas* spp. *B. cepacia* exhibited 100% resistance to ceftazidime (data not shown), meropenem, and levofloxacin, while *Acinetobacter* spp. showed 100% resistance to cefotaxime and ceftazidime and 80% resistance to gentamicin (data not shown). Additionally, 80% of the *Acinetobacter* spp. isolates were resistant to cefepime, piperacillin-tazobactam, meropenem, and levofloxacin, whereas only 33.3% of *Pseudomonas* spp. isolates were resistant to these antibiotics. None of the

Fig. 2. Antimicrobial resistance pattern of Gram-positive cocci.

Fig. 3. Antimicrobial resistance pattern of Enterobacterales (n=13).

isolates tested positive for extended-spectrum beta-lactamase or carbapenemase production.

Among 54 patients who underwent ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunting, 31.5% required re-shunting, and 14.8% died due to various complications.

DISCUSSION

Since its introduction in 1908, ventriculoperitoneal CSF shunting has remained a cornerstone in the management of hydrocephalus, substantially reducing morbidity and mortality [18]. In the present study, the infection rate

among VP shunt recipients was 44.4%, considerably higher than the rates reported in most previous studies. Benachinmardi et al. documented an infection rate of 14.8% [19], Woo et al. reported 6.7% in a Hong Kong cohort [20], and Sarguna et al. observed only 3.98% [21]. Muram et al. found an infection rate of 5.8% in adults [22], while Arslan et al. reported an infection rate of 19.3% among pediatric patients [23].

Our results indicate a persistently high rate of ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunt infection. A high number of infectious cases suggests persistent challenges in infection prevention strategies. The ability of bacteria

Fig. 4. Antimicrobial resistance pattern of non-fermenters (n=9).

to form a protective biofilm on the shunt could be one of the major reasons for the higher infection rate, as this could contribute to immune evasion and antimicrobial resistance, making infections difficult to treat, even with the use of systemic or intraventricular antibiotics. Other possible contributing factors include gaps in operating theatre sterility protocols, lack of antibiotic-impregnated catheters, and the emergence of multidrug-resistant organisms, notably *Pseudomonas* spp., *Acinetobacter* spp., and *Staphylococcus* spp., which are well recognized as agents of hospital-acquired infections. These findings highlight the urgent need to strengthen infection control practices, ensure strict adherence to aseptic techniques, and consider antibiotic-impregnated or silver-coated shunt systems where resources permit.

According to studies performed by Benachinmardi et al. [19], Muram et al. [22], Sarguna et al. [21], and Woo et al. [20], more male patients were infected after VP shunting: 67.08%, 63.6%, 77.7% and 66.6%, respectively. In contrast, our findings showed equal numbers of male and female patients with infection, indicating no gender preponderance in this cohort.

In our study children aged <10 years represented the largest proportion of infected cases (14.8%). The contributing factors in this pediatric group included congenital hydrocephalus (33.3%), low birth weight

(16.7%), and developmental delay (4.2%). Notably, congenital hydrocephalus was significantly associated with VP shunt infection ($p=0.016$), which may reflect the complexity of the condition, shunt placement at an earlier age, and increased exposure to hospital environments.

Adults over 40 years accounted for 13.7% of infections, likely influenced by a higher prevalence of intracranial tumors (54.1%) and CNS infection (4.2%), as well as age-related immune decline (Tables 1 and 2). In contrast, other studies have reported higher infection rates in adults: Asif et al. recorded a mean patient age of 36.7 ± 19.3 years [24], while Woo et al. reported a mean age of 48 years [20], and Benachinmardi et al. found a peak incidence between 45 and 50 years of age [19]. Despite these observations, our data showed no statistically significant association between age group and infection incidence, suggesting that the observed differences may be due to random variation.

In terms of risk factors associated with VP shunt infection, our results for congenital hydrocephalus align closely with those of McGirt et al. (34.8%) [10]. However, we observed a higher prevalence of cranial tumors (54.1%) than that reported by Campbell et al. (14.7%) [25], Morissette et al. (18.4%) [26], and Woo et al. (30%) [20]. Post-traumatic hydrocephalus was not encountered in our series, whereas Morissette et al. reported it in 5.3% of infected patients [26]. The frequency of CNS infection

in our study (4.2%) was comparable to that described by Mostafavi et al. (4.29%) [27], but slightly lower than the rates reported by Morissette et al. (7.9%) [26] and Woo et al. (8%) [20].

In the present study, headache was the most frequent clinical symptom of VP shunt infection (41.7%), likely reflecting the mechanical stretching of the meninges caused by hydrocephalus. Other common manifestations included vomiting (41.7%), reduced vision (20.8%), fever (20.8%), and dizziness (12.5%). Kumar et al. similarly identified headache as the leading symptom (78.5%), followed by vomiting (75.9%), fever (73.4%), decreased consciousness (63.3%), seizures (26.6%), and blurred vision (13.9%) [28]. In contrast, Paff et al. [29] suggested that fever is generally the most common presentation, although they also listed vomiting and headache as typical features.

Regarding microbiology, monomicrobial growth was detected in 40.7% (22/54) of all samples in our study, whereas polymicrobial growth was detected in only 3.7% of samples. Benachinmardi et al. and Kumar et al. also reported predominantly monomicrobial infections [19, 28], which is in accordance with our data, whereas Woo et al. found a significantly higher polymicrobial rate of 17% [20]. The predominance of monomicrobial infections in our cohort may reflect the normally sterile nature of the cerebrospinal fluid and the protective role of an intact blood–brain barrier.

In the current study, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was the most common isolate (16.7%), followed by *Acinetobacter* spp. (9.3%), *E. coli* (7.4%), *Pseudomonas* spp. (5.4%), coagulase-negative staphylococci (3.7%), and *Burkholderia cepacia*, *S. aureus*, and *Candida* spp. (each 1.9%). Overall, Gram-negative bacteria predominated, a finding consistent with Benachinmardi et al. [19] and Asif et al., who reported Gram-negative organisms in 76% versus Gram-positive organisms in 24% of isolates – *Acinetobacter* species (41%), *Pseudomonas* species (16%), coagulase-negative staphylococci (13%), *S. aureus* (10%), *Klebsiella* species (10%), and *E. coli* (8%) [24]. Other studies have highlighted *K. pneumoniae* and *E. coli* as frequent Gram-negative pathogens [21, 30], which is similar to the findings of present study.

By contrast, Mostafavi et al. in an Iranian pediatric neurosurgery ward identified Gram-positive bacteria – notably coagulase-negative staphylococci, *Enterococcus* spp., and *S. aureus* – as the main causes of VP shunt infection, followed by Gram-negative organisms such as *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Enterobacter* spp., and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [27]. Kumar et al. also reported a higher proportion of Gram-positive isolates [28], which contradicts the findings of the present study. These differing pathogen profiles across regions likely

reflect local antimicrobial stewardship practices, infection control policies, and the emergence of multidrug-resistant strains, which together shape the microbiological landscape of VP shunt infection.

A sufficient concentration of gentamicin in CSF could not be achieved by systemic administration because of the limited penetration of the blood–brain barrier. In cases of VP shunt infection, direct instillation of gentamicin into the shunt reservoir or via the intraventricular route allows for high local antibiotic levels, enhancing bactericidal activity against biofilm-forming pathogens such as *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. When combined with appropriate systemic therapy, this approach is associated with clinical improvement [31, 32].

In our cohort, Gram-positive isolates exhibited complete resistance to penicillin (100%) and a 33.3% resistance rate to gentamicin. No resistance to vancomycin or linezolid was observed. A similar pattern was reported from Nepal in 2015, where all Gram-positive isolates remained vancomycin-susceptible [33]. Asif et al. documented high penicillin resistance in *S. aureus* (74.8%) and CoNS (83.3%) [24]. Mostafavi et al. reported lower resistance to glycopeptides (17.0%) and aminoglycosides (42.2%) [28].

Among Gram-negative organisms, *E. coli* showed the greatest resistance to aztreonam (75%), followed by cefotaxime and cefepime (50% each). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* exhibited highest resistance to cefotaxime (77.8%) and levofloxacin (66.6%). Non-fermenting organisms demonstrated extensive resistance: *Burkholderia cepacia* was resistant to ceftazidime, meropenem and levofloxacin (all 100%), while *Acinetobacter* spp. showed 100% resistance to cefotaxime and ceftazidime and high resistance to multiple other agents (cefepime, piperacillin–tazobactam, meropenem, gentamicin, levofloxacin). Comparable findings were reported by Mostafavi et al., who noted the marked resistance of Gram-negative bacteria to third generation cephalosporins, carbapenems, fluoroquinolones, and aminoglycosides [27]. Asif et al. similarly observed high resistance of *Pseudomonas* species to ceftazidime (69.9%), with combined susceptibility of all Gram-negative isolates to third-generation cephalosporins falling below 30% [24].

These variations in antimicrobial resistance across studies likely reflect geographical differences and local prescribing practices. Current recommendations for treating carbapenem-resistant *A. baumannii* include high-dose ampicillin–sulbactam combined with at least one other active agent (such as polymyxin B, minocycline, tigecycline, or cefiderocol). In India,

most carbapenem-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacteria produce carbapenemases, mainly metallo- β -lactamase (MBL) enzymes, and treatment options are limited. Although cefiderocol remains active against this infection, it is not currently widely available in India. Therefore, colistin-based combination therapy is considered the most practical alternative for MBL-producing or other difficult-to-treat *P. aeruginosa* infections [12].

The clinical outcomes in our series were poor compared to those in many published studies. Re-shunting was required in 31.5% of patients, and the mortality rate was 14.8%. Mostafavi et al. observed shunt replacement in 26.4% of cases, a rate similar to ours, whereas Muram et al. reported a higher re-shunting frequency of 46.8% [22, 27]. Mortality rates reported elsewhere were lower: 6.1% by Mostafavi et al. [27] and 6.1% by Campbell et al. [25], with Sarguna et al. recording no deaths [21]. The high re-shunting and significantly higher mortality rates in our study likely reflect the greater prevalence of multidrug-resistant pathogens, which complicate therapy, increase treatment failure, and necessitate repeated procedures, each carrying an additional infection risk. This burden may have been exacerbated by the higher frequency of underlying risk factors identified in our patient population.

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CONCLUSIONS

Despite advances in neurosurgical techniques, ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunt infection remains a frequent and serious complication with a substantial risk of mortality. The etiology of these infections varies across healthcare settings, reflecting local pathogen prevalence and resistance patterns. Treatment is particularly challenging because infections often involve bacteria with high antimicrobial resistance levels.

Meticulous operating theatre practice, strict aseptic techniques, and comprehensive preoperative preparation of patients are essential for reducing infection rates. Given the limited literature on VP shunt infections, there is a pressing need for large multicenter surveillance studies and investigations of bundle-based infection prevention strategies to inform global best practices.

LIMITATIONS

1. Sample size and setting: The relatively small cohort (n=54) and single-center design limited the generalizability of these findings.
2. Study design: The absence of a control group and short follow-up period restricted the strength of causal inferences.
3. Microbiological methods: Automated identification techniques, such as MALDI-TOF or VITEK, were not employed, which may have affected the precision of species-level identification.

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